

Spatial/temporal analysis of the spread in the USA of the initial virus epidemic and its correlation with prevalent wind directions and velocities

EVIDENCE OF INTENTIONAL INFECTING OF THE AMERICAN PUBLIC

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Coronavirus hot spots

Total number of coronavirus cases, per capita, in counties with two or more confirmed cases.

JET STREAM and AIRFLOW MAP : Feb, 2020

Important Dates and Locations of USA First Case Virus Detection

20 January 2020 Seattle WA

- 26 January 2020 Tempe AZ
distance from Seattle approx 1800 miles
along wind direction on above map
- 1 march 2020 New York NY
- distance from Tempe approx 4000 miles
- along wind direction on above map

Epidemic and Wind Velocities

- Epidemic velocity from Seattle to Tempe
- Distance/ time = $1800/6 = 300$ miles/day
- This corresponds to a velocity of 12 mph
- This is similar to the average wind velocity which was observed in the southwest at that time
- Epidemic velocity from Tempe to New York
- Distance/time = $4000/33 = 120$ miles/day = 5 mph
- A reasonable wind velocity for its particular path
- Given this synchronicity, the spatial/temporal path of the epidemic and the major wind path closely coincide.

ANALYSIS OF POSSIBLE SOURCES PROVES ENEMIES OF THE USA DELIBERATELY INFECTED THE AMERICAN PEOPLE

- An old truism of fluid dynamics: Where there's a flow, there must be a source
- The above evidence implies that NW winds brought the flow of virus droplets to Seattle
- How did these winds become carriers?
- Natural sources zero probability
- Only realistic source is injection and seeding of the winds by off-shore enemies of the USA
- By rocket from fishing boat in international waters or from airplane in Pacific airspace easily done
- Satellite observations can add more proof to this analysis

ADDITIONAL EVIDENCE OF DELIBERATE ACTIONS IN THIS VIRUS ATTACK

- CHINESE Dr. YAN PROVED THAT VIRUS IS SYNTHETIC AND DESIGNED FOR BIORWARFARE
- CONFIRMED BY EX-HEAD OF BRITISH INTELLIGENCE
- VIRUS CAN EXIST FOR MONTHS AT FREEZER OR REFRIGERATOR TEMPERATURES WHICH ARE PREVALENT IN THESE HIGH ALTITUDE WINDS
- ON JAN 14 CHINA/WHO CLAIMED THAT VIRUS WAS NOT CONTAGIOUS, CLOSE TO THE PROBABLE DATE WHEN THE NW WINDS WERE SEEDED IN THE NORTH PACIFIC
- NOT UNTIL OCT 5 DID CDC ADMIT VIRUS CAN BE TRANSMITTED THROUGH AIR CURRENTS AND WINDS
- THESE DATES SHOW A HIDDEN AGENDA AND DELIBERATE DECEIT TO COVER-UP THIS BIORWARFARE ATTACK ON THE WESTERN DEMOCRACIES AND ITS ECONOMIES